

Physical Constraints on dx and dt and Quantum versus Classical Mechanics

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Classical mechanics uses the notion of dx and dt regions, but assumes they may shrink to zero. This is consistent with the notion of the center-of-mass of a particle being a mathematical point and with constant velocity in a tiny dx . A changing velocity within dx does not allow dx to tend to 0.

We have argued in previous notes for the existence of a finite lower bound for dx and dt , but such a constraint would need to be implemented physically. This leads to two considerations. First, x, t are part of a 4-vector and lengths and time intervals depend on the frame so one would expect special relativity to be involved. Secondly, one might expect dt and dx lower bounds to depend on physical attributes of the particle, as it is not clear what else they might depend on. In such a way, they would be linked to special relativity instead of being arbitrary constants which would change in different relativistic frames. It seems the only physical properties of a free particle are rest mass m_0 , E , p and v . v is consistent with dx tending to 0, so it is probably not the key variable. We consider a rest frame, m_0 at rest. Then $v=p=0$ and m_{occ} is the only variable. X may be a point, so one has dt and only one variable $m_{occ}=E$ which may be associated with it. As in previous notes, we suggest that degeneracy of $A = -Et + px$ lead to the dx , dt intervals.

The notion of dt and dx intervals linked to E, p and associated with probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ means that one cannot have $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ even if p is constant. This is a paradox, however, because \hbar/p means that there is always a two-slit apparatus which can cause interference, but v constant (from $p = \text{constant}$) implies that one may have $dx \rightarrow 0$. This latter feature is characteristic of classical mechanics, while the former of quantum mechanics. As a result, if one were to ignore \hbar/p and only focus on v constant in a tiny dx one would have classical mechanics, even though technically \hbar/p does not disappear and may be experimentally manifested.

As a result, we argue that quantum mechanics does not reproduce classical mechanics in a high energy limit. First, one has the interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s which create a wavefunction which is not associated with a constant p within dx or even a constant p_{rms} . Secondly, even if one were to approximate the dx region with $\exp(ip_{rms} x)$, this would mean that its size cannot be less than \hbar/p_{rms} which contradicts the classical notion of shrinking dx to 0.

Classical Mechanics and the Shrinking of dx and dt to Zero

We argue that a key point of classical mechanics is that one considers dx and dt intervals (needed for the definition $v = dx/dt$), but that these intervals may shrink to 0. For $v = \text{constant}$, this shrinking notion also holds, but not for a velocity which changes within dx . Thus, classical mechanics considers $v = \text{constant}$ to first order within dx in order to allow dx to shrink to zero.

A Lower Bound On dx and dt

We have suggested in previous notes that there should be a lower bound on the values of dx and dt, which breaks with classical mechanics. Given that x and t create a 4-vector and one cannot have fixed constants due to time and length contractions in special relativity, we suggest that one must link lower bounds on dt and dx to special relativity. We also argue that dx and dt bounds must be physically manifested. We suggest then that dx and dt can only depend on physical variables present, which are linked with Lorentz transformations. The physical variables are m_0 , v , p and E . m_0 is really E in the rest frame and v allows for $dx \rightarrow 0$ which is something we do not desire. We thus consider E and p and try to consider a Lorentz invariant so one may find these dx and dt intervals in all frames. As suggested in previous notes, we use the degeneracy of:

$$A = -Et + px = \text{Lorentz invariant} \quad ((1))$$

This leads to $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ ($n = \text{integer}$) or $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. ((2)) In the rest frame, one may have a math point represent the center-of-mass, but dt may only be linked with m_0 because it is the only physical variable present. This is consistent with ((2)).

The above ideas lead to complex probabilities of $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. Here we already see a paradox. $p = \text{constant}$ means $v = \text{constant}$. $v = \text{constant}$ means that the notion of $dx \rightarrow 0$ holds, while p means that one has a minimal $dx = \hbar/p$. As long as there is no interaction, using $x = vt$ and considering $dx \rightarrow 0$ is fine, but \hbar/hp is associated with a physical interference from 2-slits separated by about \hbar/p and cannot be dismissed. One might think, at this point, that the classical assumption of a constant v to first order within dx is fine, but quantum mechanics uses a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s and so cannot have a constant v within a dx . In other words, quantum mechanics utilizes the wavefunction:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Even if one considers prms from KE average = $.5 \text{ prms}(x)$ $\text{prms}(x) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ ((3)), there should be a notion of $\hbar/\text{prms}(x)$ at x centered in dx and so one cannot shrink dx to zero. This itself means that even though motion may be viewed classically using $v\text{rms}(x)$, there are still physical interaction regions about each x and so $dx \rightarrow 0$ only applies to motion, not interaction. Physicality, however, is associated with interaction, we argue.

High Energy Limit of Quantum Mechanics

We argue that in the high energy limit of ((3)), one has very narrowly spaced crests and troughs, but that they are still finite and so one does not have a constant $\text{prms}(x)$ at any x point. Thus, there is no notion of $dx \rightarrow 0$ for quantum mechanics. Even if one were to approximate the situation by $\text{prms}(x)$ treated as a constant within dx , one would still need to have a minimum dx length $\hbar/\text{prms}(x)$ and this cannot become 0. If $\hbar/\text{prms}(x)$, however, is incredibly small, it is as if one has a $dx \rightarrow 0$ and a constant $v(x)$ in dx to first order. Thus, we argue that classical mechanics is an approximation of quantum mechanics at high energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical mechanics considers dx and dt intervals, but then shrinks them to 0. A constant v , is consistent with this shrinking as is the notion of a center-of-mass point. An accelerating mass cannot have v constant, but classical mechanics approximates $v(x)$ being constant to first order in dx and then shrinks dx to 0.

We argue that there should be minimal dx and dt lengths, but this immediately brings in the notion of special relativity because length and time intervals change in different frames. We argue that these dx and dt intervals must be based on physical considerations, i.e. physical variables. For a free particle, these are m_0 , E , p and v . v is linked with $dx \rightarrow 0$, and m_{occ} is really E in the rest frame, so we use E and p and the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which leads to degeneracies of $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$. This, in turn, is linked with $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ and the complex probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$.

As a result, for a constant p , v one seems to have a paradox. v constant is consistent with $dx \rightarrow 0$ for motion, but in terms of interaction, there is a minimal $dx = \hbar/p$. In the case of a bound state, one uses $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which means there exists a $p_{\text{rms}}(x)$ through $p_{\text{rms}}(x) p_{\text{rms}}(x) / 2m = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W}$ which is never constant. Classically, however, $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ would be treated as a constant at x in dx , but at the same time there is an $\hbar/p_{\text{rms}}(x)$ region (linked to interaction) which cannot shrink to zero.

These considerations hold even in the high energy limit. If one were to replace $W(x)$ with $\exp(ip_{\text{rms}}(x)x)$ at each x (with dx), there still remains $\hbar/p_{\text{rms}}(x)$ and so dx cannot formally shrink to 0. If $\hbar/p_{\text{rms}}(x)$, however, is so small that one cannot possibly resolve it, one may use the approximation that $dx \rightarrow 0$. Thus, we argue that classical mechanics is an approximation of quantum mechanics, but that quantum mechanics does not formally lead to $dx \rightarrow 0$ even at high energy.